

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D9.2 Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities Report - First version

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Glossary and Abbreviations

CAM	Cathode Active Material
CDS	Communication and Dissemination Strategy
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
PDER	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SSB	Solid State Battery
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
XPS	X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

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Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and training efforts carried out by our consortium during the first 15 months of the project, spanning from its initiation in August 2022 to October 2023. As part of SPINMATE CDS, it outlines the steps taken to achieve our communication and dissemination objectives, as originally set forth in the PEDR.

In this report, we will detail the various activities conducted in line with the Communication, Dissemination, and Training Strategy established by the SPINMATE consortium. These activities encompass:

- (i) **Communication Activities:** To raise awareness about EU initiatives and promoting the SPINMATE project, along with its outcomes, to a diverse range of target audiences.
- (ii) **Dissemination Activities:** To facilitate the transfer of knowledge generated during the project to ensure that the results are accessible for utilization by others, using various means.
- (iii) **Training Activities:** To enable both industrialists and research infrastructures to harness the knowledge generated effectively, our training initiatives are designed to enhance understanding and utilization of project-derived insights, extending the impact of SPINMATE beyond its immediate scope.

This report will offer an insightful account of how these activities have been executed, with a keen emphasis on the alignment with our strategic goals and the progress achieved over the stated timeframe.

1. Communication

1.1 Project Identity

INOVA+ developed the branding material of SPINMATE project; the logo and formats selected establish the identity of the project.

In the process of conceptualizing the SPINMATE logo, INOVA+ have diligently strived to establish a direct and meaningful connection with groups and stakeholders closely aligned with the fields of batteries and electric vehicles. The main goal was to ensure that the project's visual representation effectively communicates its relevance and objectives to these target audiences. This branding material is instrumental in supporting the overall mission and goals of the SPINMATE project.

1.2 Media Channels

As presented in D9.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER), SPINMATE developed a project website (www.spinmate.eu) as the primary communication channel, and social media presence on X (former Twitter) (https://twitter.com/spinmate_eu) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/spinmate>). The social media channels are regularly monitored by INOVA+, with a direct support from ABEE. Project partners are actively involved and support the dissemination of publications as well as help to create content for new publications based on the project findings.

Project Website

The website offers an in-depth introduction to the SPINMATE project, providing an extensive narrative about its inception, goals, and overall significance. Visitors can learn about the project's objectives, its role within the Horizon EU initiative, and the broader context of sustainable energy solutions and electric mobility.

- **Key Announcements:** The platform serves as a real-time communication hub for project announcements and important deliverables and milestones. Whether it's the launch of a new research phase, the acquisition of noteworthy partners, or significant achievements, this section keeps stakeholders informed and engaged.
- **Project Results:** The "News" section showcases the outcomes of the SPINMATE project, including research findings, innovations, and technological advancements. This resource is invaluable for researchers, industry professionals, and anyone interested in the project's tangible impact on the energy and electric vehicle sectors.
- **Marketing Materials:** The website acts as a central repository for a range of marketing materials that help convey the project's message effectively. Users can access brochures, technical reports, videos, and interactive multimedia resources that offer a deeper insight into the project's activities and innovations.
- **News Updates:** Besides key announcements, the site features a continuous stream of news updates. These articles provide detailed information about ongoing project activities, collaborative efforts, and any relevant industry or policy developments related to electric vehicles and sustainable energy.
- **Interactive Features:** To enhance user engagement, the website includes interactive elements such as contact forums, and the opportunity to collaborate with the SPINMATE partners. These features foster a sense of community among stakeholders and allow for active participation in the project's discourse.

- Social Media Integration:** In parallel with the website, SPINMATE maintains a strong presence on various social media platforms, including *LinkedIn* and *X*. These platforms are used to amplify the project's visibility, connect with a broader audience, and facilitate discussions on related topics.

Figure 1 – Website capture (I)

Figure 2 – Website capture (II)

Partnership

- [ALL](#)
- [DELIVERABLES](#)
- [MEET THE PARTNERS](#)
- [NEWSLETTER](#)
- [PARTNERSHIP](#)**

Figure 3 – Website capture (III)

Deliverables

- [D1.1 Management Handbook >](#)
- [D1.2 Data Management Plan >](#)
- [D1.4 Gender Equality Action Plan >](#)
- [D2.1 Technical requirements for small \(1Ah\) and large \(10Ah\) battery cells and protocols for testing >](#)
- [D3.2 Report on the conclusions of the dedicated workshops >](#)
- [D9.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - PDER >](#)

Figure 4 – Website capture (IV)

Meet the partners

[ALL](#)

[DELIVERABLES](#)

[MEET THE PARTNERS](#)

[NEWSLETTER](#)

[PARTNERSHIP](#)

Meet the partners on 25 May 2023

[MEET THE PARTNERS-ABEE](#)

[READ MORE](#)

Meet the partners on 25 May 2023

[MEET THE PARTNERS-ISCF](#)

[READ MORE](#)

Figure 5 – Website capture (V)

Social Media

The SPINMATE LinkedIn page stands as a pivotal component of a comprehensive dissemination project strategy, delivering substantial outcomes and contributing significantly to the project's success. With over *350 followers* and a rapidly expanding professional network, the platform has proven to be a powerful tool for engaging our target audience and elevating our project's visibility and brand recognition. The top three job function categories of our visitors in LinkedIn are Engineering (27%), Research (14%), and Program and Project Manager (10%); while the top three of industry areas of our visitors are Automation Machinery Manufacturing (33%), research Services (18%), and Appliances, Electrical, and Electronics Manufacturing (17%).

- **Follower Growth and Network Expansion:** The fact that we have surpassed 350 followers on the SPINMATE LinkedIn page is indicative of the platform's success in fostering a robust community of stakeholders. It has allowed us to extend our professional network, connecting with individuals and organizations closely aligned with our project's objectives. This network expansion has created opportunities for collaboration, partnerships, and valuable insights.
- **Content Engagement:** The LinkedIn page has been instrumental in boosting engagement with our content. By sharing relevant and informative posts, we have positioned ourselves as thought leaders in our field. This not only enhances our project's credibility but also encourages valuable discussions and knowledge sharing among our followers.
- **Event Promotion and Feedback Collection:** Our LinkedIn page has played a crucial role in promoting project-related events. This promotion has led to increased event attendance and engagement. Moreover, it serves as a platform for collecting insightful feedback from our audience, helping us continually refine and improve our project initiatives.

Moving on to the **SPINMATE X/Twitter page**, which currently boasts approximately *50 followers*, while the user engagement may be more selective compared to LinkedIn, it serves as a complementary channel with distinct advantages:

Targeted User Engagement: X attracts a narrower scope of users but excels in engaging with policy makers and other EU projects. This is particularly strategic for disseminating news, updates, and real-time information, making it a key resource for stakeholders seeking immediate and concise updates on project developments.

In summary, our social media strategy, led by the SPINMATE's *LinkedIn* and *X* pages, has been effective in achieving our dissemination objectives.

1.3 Promotional Materials

INOVA+ (with the close support from SPINMATE partners) has been developing a group of promotional materials to support project communication and dissemination. Below is listed the materials developed in the first 15 months of the project.

Flyer

The first promotional material developed was a flyer (triptych).

Figure 6 – SPINMATE triptych

The Flyer is the material which contains the general information about the project. This material is a document that can be printed on both sides and folded in three – easily to distribute and handover to contacts and participants during events, networking, and other activities in which SPINMATE partners can participate. The flyer serves as a valuable resource for those who have recently been introduced to the project or anyone seeking a quick overview, as it describes the project scope and expected impacts in a nutshell.

By October 2023, the flyer registers 291 interactions through LinkedIn and 373 through X users.

Meet the Partners

INOVA+ launched an online initiative in collaboration with the project partners, which involves the creation of a series of individual questionnaires. These questionnaires are designed to engage and interact with the project followers, website visitors and anyone who seeks deeper insights into the SPINMATE project, as well as the crucial roles of the project partners.

This innovative approach allows to provide a more personal and human touch to SPINMATE project's communication strategy. By conducting these interviews, INOVA+ aims to introduce the

members of the dedicated team behind SPINMATE to the audience. In doing so, the consortium not only gives a face to the individuals who are driving the project forward but also shed light on the passion and expertise that they bring to the table. Furthermore, these interviews serve as a unique opportunity to showcase the key activities undertaken by our project partners. This includes highlighting their specific contributions, expertise, and the collaborative efforts that are propelling SPINMATE towards its objectives. It offers a valuable perspective on the intricate network of expertise and knowledge that is the foundation of our project's success. In addition to humanizing SPINMATE project, these interviews will also provide insight into the expected impacts that the project is poised to make in the field.

It aims to elucidate how the combined efforts of the partners, with their diverse skill sets and shared commitment, are driving innovations, promoting sustainability, and making tangible contributions to the areas of energy and electric mobility.

The table below presents the captures made in social media to promote the dissemination of the interviews. This initiative will continue in the following months.

Table 1 – SPINMATE “Meet the Partners” status by M15

Partner	Advertisement for the SPINMATE “Meet the Partners” initiative
<p>ABEE interview</p>	<p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>

Partner	Advertisement for the SPINMATE “Meet the Partners” initiative
<p>TME interview</p>	<p>Laurent Castro Senior Engineer Battery team TME</p> <p>Aurélie Guéguen Senior Engineer Battery team TME</p> <p>Definition of the pilot line requirements based on the KPIs the battery cells will achieve is essential to ensure a proper industrialization process of cell manufacturing. Optimization of all SPINMATE pilot line parameters from the beginning based on a well-designed battery cell will allow to align all the different cursors on the right position and provide an accurate control of the battery cells production in the road of industrialization...</p> <p>SPINMATE</p> <p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>
<p>ISCF interview</p>	<p>Andreas Gronbach Senior Expert Lithium-Ion Process Development</p> <p>Philip Daubinger Research scientist</p> <p>Next-generation batteries will use lithium metal as one component in the cell. One problem is the immediate formation of blocking surface species due to reaction with water or air. We are therefore using a patented sandblasting technique, similar to the one your dentist uses to clean your teeth, to clean the surface of the lithium metal. For validation, we integrate the freshly cleaned lithium into the batteries. This optimization step increases the performance of the batteries..</p> <p>SPINMATE</p> <p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>
<p>CEA interview</p>	<p>Anh Linh Research engineer on battery systems</p> <p>I am very happy to contribute to the development of an innovative battery altogether with all the partners of the project. Each partner has a very strong knowledge, and we are going to share and learn many things. I am waiting impatiently for the first cells to know their performances. In SPINMATE, we have the chance to develop very concrete products: cells, a pilot line, a module tested in representative conditions. Additionally, what is extremely important to me, is that the technology that we are going to develop will also be assessed on the environmental part: a life cycle analysis will be done, and recycling will be studied. I feel this is essential to give sense to our work and be convinced of our new technology.</p> <p>SPINMATE</p> <p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>

Partner	Advertisement for the SPINMATE “Meet the Partners” initiative
<p>COMAU interview</p>	<p>Daniela Fontana Solutions Development Leader</p> <p>I am enthusiastic about seeing by the end of the project a complete production line for large format solid-state battery cells and the validation at pilot level of the results achieved in the laboratory. I am also excited thinking about the benefits that the application of innovative digitalization tools will provide to R&D and industrial communities. The approach to product and process development and control, now mainly based on trial-and-error, will change thanks to a deeper understanding of the correlations among the different factors involved in manufacturing. I think that both results will really represent a big step forward for the implementation of mass production of solid-state batteries.</p> <p>SPINMATE</p> <p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>
<p>TUBS interview</p>	<p>Rezvan Karimi Research associate</p> <p>Kevin Voges Research associate</p> <p>In the production process of battery electrodes, a homogeneous distribution and dispersion of all particulate components are crucial to release the full performance of a battery cell. For SSB where solid-solid-contacts are responsible for the ion and electron exchange between active material, solid electrolyte and carbon additives, a suitable particle arrangement is even more important compared to cells with liquid electrolytes.</p> <p>SPINMATE</p> <p>Read more in the full interview as part of our engaging Meet the Partners series!</p>

Promotional Videos

INOVA+ developed a promotional video to introduce SPINMATE. This video serves as a dynamic introduction to the project, offering a concise yet comprehensive overview of its primary goals, anticipated impact, and the valuable collaboration of our esteemed partners. This video serves as a dynamic introduction to the project, offering a concise yet comprehensive overview of its primary goals, anticipated impact, and the valuable collaboration of SPINMATE esteemed partners. Here below an expanded view of the various facets and potential applications of this promotional video:

- Project Introduction:** The video encapsulates the essence of the SPINMATE project, effectively communicating its core objectives and the challenges it seeks to address. It provides a high-level understanding of the project's significance in the realms of sustainable energy solutions and electric mobility, reinforcing the project identity to create a connection with viewers using project colour themes, visuals, and motto.

- **Expected Impact:** By highlighting the expected impact of the project, the video underlines its potential to make a meaningful difference in the industry. It conveys the transformative outcomes that SPINMATE aims to achieve, whether it's advancements in technology, reductions in carbon emissions, or other substantial benefits.
- **Partner Recognition:** The video recognizes the integral role of the project partners, emphasizing their collective expertise, commitment, and contributions to SPINMATE. This not only showcases the collaborative strength of the project but also fosters a sense of unity and purpose among partners.
- **Social Media Engagement:** The video is strategically designed to support audience engagement on social media platforms. Sharing it on the project website, LinkedIn, and X allows us to leverage the captivating power of visual content to reach a wider and more diverse audience. It encourages likes, shares, comments, and discussions, thereby expanding the project's digital footprint.
- **Physical Events:** In addition to its online presence, the video is a versatile tool that can be employed at physical events. By displaying it live at conferences, exhibitions, and seminars, we can attract the attention of a broad spectrum of attendees, including potential collaborators, investors, and individuals interested in the project's goals.
- **Attracting New Audiences:** The ambition to attract new audiences is a central focus of the video. Its engaging and informative content is crafted to pique the interest of those who may not yet be familiar with SPINMATE. It has the potential to draw in fresh perspectives and diverse stakeholders who can contribute to the project's success.

Figure 7 – SPINMATE promotional video capture

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7087700198306590720>

By October 2023, this promotional video registers 939 visualisations through LinkedIn and 632 through X users.

1.4 SOLID4B Cluster

Under the banner of the **SOLID4B Cluster**, SPINMATE is at the forefront of a collaborative effort involving seven EU-funded projects that share common objectives. These projects are dedicated to mutual support in the dissemination of results and are collectively committed to advancing the EU's climate transition goals.

SPINMATE is collaborating with the following projects:

- **SOLID¹**: Sustainable Manufacturing & Optimized Materials and Interfaces for Lithium Metal Batteries with Digital Quality Control.
- **PULSELION²**: Pulsed Laser Deposition Technology for Solid State Battery Manufacturing Supported by Digitalization.
- **HIDDEN³**: Hindering dendrite growth in lithium metal batteries.
- **ADVAGEN⁴**: Development of Advanced Next Generation Solid-State Batteries for Electromobility Applications.
- **HELENA⁵**: Halide Solid State Batteries for Electric Vehicles and Aircrafts.
- **AM4BAT⁶**: Gen. 4b Solid State Li-ion battery by additive manufacturing.

SPINMATE, under the collaboration effort with other related European funded projects, build a group of (above mentioned) projects to establish a solid knowledge basis around main Gen 4b SSB materials-related achievements. SOLID4B cluster works to enhance research synergies among the European-level projects working on solid state batteries, translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders. This cluster was built to synchronize and jointly promote the R&D topics in the electric vehicle field.

Thus, a cooperation framework was established with partners from other consortia, with budgeted provisions to organise dedicated webinars and workshops, and promote the networking of researchers between leading research institutions in Europe. The learned experiences from other projects will be considered, ensuring the successful implementation and impact of the SPINMATE project with related EU-funded projects and initiatives with common goals, supporting each other on dissemination of results and contributing to achieve the EU goals towards climate transition.

ABEE and INOVA+ are collaborating closely on the cluster identity and communication strategy, defining the SOLID4B branding, as well as creating and managing the LinkedIn SOLID4B cluster social media page.

Figure 8 – SOLID4B cluster Logo

¹ SOLID project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069505>

² PULSELION project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069686>

³ HIDDEN project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957202>

⁴ ADVAGEN project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069743>

⁵ HELENA project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069681>

⁶ AM4BAT project cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069756>

2. Dissemination

2.1 Newsletters

1st Newsletter

SPINMATE has released its first newsletter in May 2023. It included a brief presentation of the project, and described the consortium’s ambitions within SPINMATE. The organisation of meetings, participation in events, as well as the introduction of the Cluster was described and will be continuously updated in the upcoming newsletters (as is the case for other dissemination activities). The first results achieved in SPINMATE are described in this newsletter, particularly the (i) cell design scenarios performed by TME to achieve the expected energy density targets of 1200Wh/l and 450Wh/kg; (ii) collection of data for the development and optimisation of cell components through the development of mathematical models and processes coordinated by COMAU; and (iii) development of polymer electrolytes with excellent ionic conductivity conducted by CICE, aimed to increase electrochemical performances.

Figure 9 – First Newsletter capture

The 1st Newsletter had a total of 223 impressions through LinkedIn by October 2023.

2nd Newsletter

SPINMATE has released its second newsletter in November 2023. This edition announces the first wave of project deliverables approved and published on the website. The second project General Assembly held in Vitoria Gasteiz by CICE and the first webinar from SOLID4B cluster are highlighted as the main events organised by SPINMATE. The newsletter includes then the semestral highlights with the (i) component's development for solid-state batteries. CIC energigUNE, in collaboration with ARKEMA and CIDETEC, has developed high-performance, PVDF-based gel polymer electrolytes; (ii) optimisation and characterization of positive electrode formulation in solid-state coin cells (Li/GPE/NMC811) obtaining relevant discharge capacity and high coulombic efficiency values at room temperature; (iii) IREC conducted a series of experiments to enhance its capacity, employing various strategies to upgrade NMC811 material with O₂ calcination; (iv) collection of data for anode and cathode electrode preparation and for the electrolyte membrane production processes, a process led by COMAU. This edition also presents an update on the communication and dissemination activities, providing insights on the interviews made with partners, SOLID4B cluster upcoming hybrid workshop (December 12th, 2023) and actions performed for the training pills development.

Figure 10 – Second Newsletter capture

The second newsletter was published on October 27th, and it counts already with 816 impressions on LinkedIn.

2.2 Webinars

First SOLID4B webinar

The first webinar of the **SOLID4B webinar series** took place on the 26th of June, 2023, from 10.00 AM to 12.30 PM under the name "*Lithium metal anode production methods: State of the art*,"

challenges, and future perspective". The event was promoted online via social media, coordinated by INOVA+ and ABEE with the support of all projects involved from their respective networks.

Figure 11 – SOLID4B 1st webinar announcement capture

The agenda (see Figure 12) for this webinar compiled a group of individual presentations to disseminate innovative research work and achievements made in SOLID4B cluster Projects. This webinar focused on the different Lithium metal anode production methods that are utilised in the *SOLID4B cluster European projects*. The session was opened by SOLID4B founders Takwa Benissa and Andrea Martinez (**SPINMATE**), who explained the **SOLID4B cluster** goals and scope, as well as introduced the involved partners. The session – moderated by ABEE – was divided into the following topics (and respective presenters):

- 1) Welcome – SOLID4B cluster presentation (SOLID4B cluster founder)
- 2) General Topic Introduction:
 - a. Lithium metal anode production methods (ADVAGEN)
 - b. Self-healing methods for the Lithium method electrode (HIDDEN)
- 3) Vapor-based Techniques:
 - a. Evaporation and sputtering processes for Lithium metal deposition (SPINMATE)
 - b. PLD of Li metal and protective coatings (PULSELION)
 - c. ALD coatings to stabilize Lithium (SOLID)
- 4) Electrodeposition/Free Anode
 - a. Electrochemical Lithium production from anode-less battery (AM4BAT)
- 5) Industrial scale production
 - a. Processing lithium metal by extrusion (SEATBELT).

The session closed with a roundtable discussion on the analysis and conclusions from the different techniques – moderated by BEPA.

The talk representing SPINMATE "Evaporation and Sputtering Processes for the Deposition of Lithium Metal and its Protective Coatings," was presented by Joel Omale from ABEE. Abstract: *The goal of attaining an energy density of 500 Wh/kg required for automotive applications is likely only possible by adopting lithium-metal batteries, which are batteries that have lithium metal as the anode. To date, the large-scale production of lithium metal films is chiefly by extrusion, which is expensive and produces films with irreproducible properties, hampering the progress of lithium-metal batteries. Physical vapor deposition, in contrast, produces lithium metal films with more controllable and reproducible properties. In this talk, the manufacturing of lithium metal films and protective coatings by thermal evaporation and sputtering is elucidated, and recommendations will be made about the more suitable technique for each material class.*

ABEE and INOVA+ coordinated the organisation and communication of the event.

Figure 12 – SOLID4B 1st webinar Agenda

This event had 107 participants from academia, research, industry, and policy/regulatory bodies across European countries.

2.3 External Events

- (1) Solid State batteries V in Frankfurt/Main on 22-24th November 2022
TME – partner responsible for the technical requirements analysis in WP2 - gathered last progress on SSB.

reference: <https://bunsen.de/>

- (2) TechBlick in Berlin on 15-16th February 2023 (online)

TME – partner responsible for the technical requirements analysis in WP2 - gathered last progress on SSB.

reference: <https://www.techblick.com/pastevents>

(3) RTR Conference in Brussels on 14-16th February 2023.

ABEE participated at the discussion on State-of-the-art of European funded research projects under road transportation.

#RTRConference2023: All about synergies

(4) eMobility Expo World Congress 2023 in Valencia on 22nd March 2023.

An oral presentation was given by IREC on electrode materials and next-generation battery technologies including one slide presenting the SPINMATE project.

reference: <https://www.emobilityworldcongress.com/exhibit/exhibit-solutions/>

(5) The Battery Show Europe & Electric & Hybrid Vehicle Technology Expo Europe at Messe Stuttgart on 23-25th May 2023.

Over 10,000 attendees.

CIDETEC Energy Storage participated via Booth# 10-J86.

ABEE had a presential discussion with industrial suppliers for machine & equipment. Links and introduction made to the needs for projects with similar approaches of SPINMATE (cathode coating, assembly, etc.).

reference: <https://www.thebatteryshow.eu/en/home.html>

- (6) ESPE23 (European Symposium & workshop on polymer electrolytes for battery applications in Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) at Karlsruhe, on 25-27 September 2023.

CICe reported the preparation and characterization of SPE by extrusion, and the comparison of its properties with the ones obtained by solvent casting. This meeting was also an opportunity to meet other leading experts for a knowledge sharing and networking on the development of polymer electrolytes.

reference: <https://www.postlithiumstorage.org/en/polis>

- (7) LCBAT12019 - Cluster Innovation and Networking days at Grenoble (FR) on 27-28 September 2023.

The four projects forming the LCBAT12019 cluster – ASTRABAT, SAFELIMOVE, SOLIDIFY and SUBLIME - presented their main outputs on the development of next-generation battery (Solid-State) during three dedicated topical sessions. **ARKEMA** participated on the *Innovation & Networking days*, a 2-day event aiming to connect the LCBAT12019 EU-funded projects to the public and key European and international stakeholders and associations, in the field of All-Solid-State Battery Technologies, by giving an oral presentation on an industrial session, disseminating SPINMATE project.

reference: LCBAT12019 Cluster

(8) RESPECT project launch event: Recycling Li-ion batteries for clean mobility (hybrid) on 5th October 2023.

ABEE discussed the Topic: "Lessons Learned from Clustering Activities" diving deep into the world of clustering and share invaluable insights gained through our experiences in both Solid4B Cluster and SPINMATE.

The RESPECT project launch event "Recycling Li-ion Batteries for Clean Mobility"

In the framework of the workshop in collaboration with [the Batteries European Partnership Association \(BEPA\)](#), the event highlighted the importance of clustering activities in improving EU-funded R&I projects' efficiency and dissemination of

results. Several clusters were presented: **Collabat** (Tomas Jezdinsky, ECI, Nerea Nieto and Eduardo Miguel, IKERLAN), **Solid4B** (Takwa Benissa and Kunsulu Nurekyeva, ABEE) and **Battery Heroes** (Georg Melzer-Venturi, EUTEMA). In the first panel discussion, panellists emphasised the fact that **building bridges** and **sharing common expertise make way for disruptive innovation**. Moreover, it is a seamless way to guarantee widescale dissemination of results. The workshop was moderated by **Wouter IJzermans**, Executive Director of BEPA.

reference: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/respect-recycling/>

(9) ECS (244) in Gothenburg, Sweden on 8-12th October 2023

TME gathered last progress on batteries general information, from the results achieved in the projects on the technical requirements, as reported on project deliverable D2.1 Technical requirements for small (1Ah) and large (10Ah) battery cells and protocols for testing.

Reference: <https://www.electrochem.org/244/>

3. Training

SPINMATE training pills are while specific communication and dissemination actions, carried out in WP9 to attract the interest of key industrial stakeholders and end users of the battery, EVs and related sectors. Therefore, this training activity aims to facilitate the acquisition of skills by industrialists and research infrastructures for exploiting the project results beyond the boundaries of the consortium. During SPINMATE life cycle three training pills targeting the workers of the battery industry and research infrastructures will be developed for reskilling and upskilling them in the new SPINMATE solutions.

3.1 1st Training pill

The first training pill was already designed and will be online in November 2023, disseminated throughout all SPINMATE channels and will also feed the SOLID4B channels.

This first training pill was focused on 6 main topics:

1. General aspects about SPINMATE project
2. Battery Materials
3. Manufacturing of cell components
4. Production Tools
5. Testing Batteries
6. The future of the technology

The SPINMATE project will commit the challenge of reaching the first milestone towards the large-scale manufacturing of generation 4b (Gen 4b) SSB cells while demonstrating the cost-effective digital-driven proof-of-concept pilot line at a TRL6 level that will comprise industry 4.0 and 5.0 digital manufacturing concepts. Upscaling solid state batteries through sustainable manufacturing processes, and design for recyclability need to be incorporated during upscaling, however material processing and tool adaptation are at the forefront of challenges. The first training pill will introduce the following five topics to facilitate the learning and understanding of knowledge applied in SPINMATE.

SPINMATE's consortium has been constituted by involving a team that covers the whole value chain of the of SSB industry, bringing together the necessary profiles, and all the expertise and resources required to secure access to more safe, durable, cost-competitive, sustainable, and higher performance, batteries for the EV sector. The consortium is composed of 13 organisations from 7 different EU countries.

The total budget of the project is 6,9M€ for a four-year duration starting from August 1st 2022 to July 31st 2026.

Figure 13 – 1st Training pill “introduction” capture

General aspects about SPINMATE project

SPINMATE project and the consortium – *“The SPINMATE project will commit the challenge of reaching the first milestone towards the large-scale manufacturing of generation 4b (Gen 4b) SSB cells while demonstrating the cost-effective digital-driven proof-of-concept pilot line at a TRL6 level that will comprise industry 4.0 and 5.0 digital manufacturing concepts. By means of different digitalisation approaches, SPINMATE processing, and*

manufacturing innovations will contribute to: (i) a sustainable and competitive large-scale production of SSBs (ii) the reduction of the carbon footprint, and (iii) the enhancement of safety along the entire value chain. Also, the developed SSB-based technologies in this project will contribute to achieving a mass electrification of the automotive sector, which has the enormous potential to reduce global GHG emissions by 16 % by 2035. SPINMATE’s consortium has been constituted by involving a team that covers the whole value chain of the of SSB industry, bringing together the necessary profiles, and all the expertise and resources required to secure access to more safe, durable, cost-competitive, sustainable, and higher performance, batteries for the EV sector. The consortium is composed of 13 organisations from 7 different EU countries. The total budget of the project is 6,9M€ for a four-year duration starting from August 1st 2022 to July 31st 2026.” **Takwa Benissa (ABEE)**

Upscaled production through innovative concepts on solid-state cell assembly – *“Upscaling solid state batteries introduces a number of challenges compared to the traditional Li-ion technology due to the properties of materials used, as well as highly resistive solid-solid interfaces. Sustainable manufacturing processes, and design for recyclability need to be incorporated during upscaling, however material processing and tool*

adaptation are at the forefront of challenges.” **Kunsulu Nurekeyeva (ABEE)**

Battery Materials

Advantages of the spray pyrolysis route for upscaling of solid-state battery cathodes – *“Spray pyrolysis has the flexibility to produce mixed oxide materials with a wide range of compositions and to swiftly change between different chemistries and dopants. The resulting powder tends to have high sinterability and very even distribution of dopants. The high sinterability resulting from small primary particles, while being a disadvantage to many*

current battery technologies could potentially be a significant benefit for sintered solid-state batteries.” **Leif Olav Jøsang (CPT)**

Manufacturing of cell components

Key challenges and R&D efforts in engineering solid-state electrolytes production – *“The main challenge in the development of solid-state electrolytes lies in achieving an optimal balance between transport and mechanical properties, electrochemical stability, processability and cost-effectiveness. Polymer electrolytes have accumulated interest due to their favourable processability and mechanical properties, however the ionic conductivity is too low for room-temperature operation (...).”* **Nicola Boaretto (CICE)**

Main challenges involved in producing cathodes for solid-state batteries (compared to conventional lithium-ion battery technology) – *“Composite positive electrodes for SSB typically comprise a cathode active material (CAM), a conductive additive, and a catholyte. To fulfil the requirements of high-performance secondary batteries, the catholyte should have a high ionic conductivity, high chemical stability, and wide*

electrochemical window. To provide sufficient ionic diffusion, positive electrode composites require a large catholyte fraction and, consequently, low volume fraction of CAM, resulting in low energy density of the final SSB (...).” **Oihane García (CIDETEC)**

Production Tools

Major manufacturing challenges and approaches faced in producing lithium metal anodes – *“The industry, at present, uses a sequence of Extrusion rolling and lamination methods to manufacture lithium metal anodes (...) the first issue is that these lithium metal anodes have an inferior surface finish and an inferior morphology; the second issue is that these have a lithium metal thickness which is too high for a high-specific energy cell.*

Lithium metal anodes having a low thickness are a key part of an all-solid state battery which has a high specific energy (...).” **Neel Sanghvi (ABEE)**

Analysing and understanding the properties and behavior of solid-state batteries – *“Several material characterization techniques are essential for analysing and understanding the properties and behaviour of solid-state batteries effectively. Among these, X-ray diffraction (XRD) is commonly used to identify crystalline phases and assess structural changes in battery materials. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron*

microscopy (TEM) provide detailed imaging and microstructural analysis, helping researchers visualize electrode and electrolyte interfaces. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy offer insights into chemical compositions and surface/interface characteristics (...).” **Marc Nel-lo (IREC)**

Techniques employed to achieve and preserve the cleanliness of lithium surfaces – *“Maintaining a clean surface of lithium metal is crucial due to its high reactivity with moisture and oxygen. Contamination on the surface can lead to the formation of a passivating layer, hindering the efficient functioning of lithium-based batteries. Primary techniques for achieving and preserving cleanliness include operating in an inert atmosphere,*

utilizing moisture-free solvents for handling and cleaning, employing specialized glove boxes or dry rooms, and employing protective coatings or passivation layers. A method to clean the surface of lithium metal is by using a sandblasting device. Sandblasting involves propelling abrasive particles at high velocity onto the surface to remove contaminants and oxides. This process effectively strips away any impurities and provides a clean surface for further processing.” **Andreas Gronbach (ISCF)**

Re-engineering of existing tools for solid-state battery – *“The production of conventional lithium-ion cells consists of three main steps: electrode manufacturing, cell assembly and cell formation. The preparation of solid-state batteries may imply changes in the first two steps: if lithium metal is used, its production process is completely different from that of conventional electrodes; in cell assembly, there will no more be the liquid electrolyte filling, but*

the in-situ production of the solid electrolyte has to be implemented. The new materials often present mechanical properties different from the conventional ones and this means that specific tools and sometimes even complete machines have to be developed to produce and handle them.” **Daniela Fontana (COMAU)**

Testing Batteries

Battery testing to evaluate its performance and ensure its safety – *"For a battery, you have to evaluate it for both performances and safety. For performances, we check that the battery provides its correct voltage, energy, and power for different conditions: different temperatures, different charge and discharge currents, but also representative profiles that simulate the electric vehicle driving cycles. We also cycle the battery with accelerated*

profiles to evaluate its lifetime. Additionally, we apply various abusive tests to be sure that the battery is safe. For instance, we deliberately force the battery to enter into thermal runaway, punching it or putting it at very high temperature, to check how it reacts in extreme conditions. A test campaign for a battery cell is therefore made of very different kind of tests before saying that the cell is validated." **Anh-Linh Bui Van (CEA)**

Cycling process of solid-state batteries, and what are the main challenges associated with maintaining consistent pressure throughout the battery's operation – *"During cycling, active material in lithium-ion batteries undergoes significant volume changes. In liquid electrolyte-based batteries, the electrolyte accommodates these fluctuations within the porous network. However, in solid-state batteries, this flexibility is absent. To*

compensate for volume changes, applying stack pressure during cycling becomes crucial. Without it, the networks for ionic and electric conductivity would be compromised, disrupting contact between the particles/polymer. Ensuring appropriate contact area between the anode and separator is another concern. Excessive pressure can deform the materials and lead to short circuits, while insufficient pressure results in limited contact area and current constriction, leading to short-circuiting. Striking the right balance is crucial for optimal battery performance." **Rezvan Karimi (TUBS)**

The future of the technology

Challenges and importance of Life Cycle Assessment conduction on SSBs – *"(..) When conducting LCA for SSBs, the main challenges are related to lack of data, especially the scale-up scenario, and the energy intensive manufacturing steps. As such, it's crucial to work closely together with technology developers to get reliable data, and use machine learning and digital models to simulate industrial scenarios. SPINMATE is applying this*

strategy with life cycle approaches for developing SSB production processes, in order to guarantee that these solutions are both economically and environmentally more sustainable." **Inês Ribeiro (INEGI)**

Battery requirements for the end users on a new and disruptive technology – *"At the end customers do not really care about what is the technology behind the Battery Electrical Vehicles. The main focus of them is more regarding the driving range, the fast charging and of course the cost. Each of customer is dreaming on having a very cheap car able to drive as long as possible and charge as fast as possible. This is exactly on what SPINMATE project will work on:*

make costumer dream a reality." **Laurent Castro (TME)**

3.2 Training Activities - Next Steps

The training materials are being compiled in a video to be shared in social media. The creation of a video compilation of SPINMATE training materials for sharing skills and knowledge within the project is a strategic move that promises to enhance the efficiency and accessibility of our training initiatives. These meticulously curated video resources, which encompass diverse aspects of our project, offer a dynamic and insightful information of imparting essential skills and knowledge to project members and stakeholders. By combining informative content with a clean design, this compilation not only ensures that the learning process is more interactive and immersive but also allows for flexibility in terms of when and where participants can access these materials. It serves as an invaluable tool to empower our followers with the skills and insights necessary for the successful execution of SPINMATE, ultimately contributing to our collective success.

4. Plan of actions for the following period

For the upcoming months, SPINMATE project is planning the following communication, dissemination, and training activities (not limited to):

- **Communication:**
 - SPINMATE banner development to use in internal/external events.
 - Meet the Partners (ongoing activity) – share of partners presentation at social media and project website.
 - Poster Template development to support project presentation by partners on external events.
- **Dissemination:**
 - 1st SOLID4B hybrid workshop: SOLID STATE LI-METAL BATTERIES TOWARDS A CIRCULAR ECONOMY: Potentials Vs. Challenges (Hybrid workshop): in Liège, Belgium, 12th December 2023
 - 3rd Newsletter (April 2024) and 4th Newsletter (October 2024).
 - Potential participation on future events:
 - CECAM school: Machine Learning Interatomic Potentials: Theory and Practice, 6-10th November 2023 Espoo, Finland.
 - Battery Innovation Days, 14-15th November 2023, Bordeaux, France (Hybrid event) with a booth at the exhibition & Participation at the Panel "Sustainable Batteries as an integral step in reducing products' carbon footprints".
 - AABC in San Diego in December 2023.
- **Training:**
 - 2nd Training Pill: This material will start to be prepared in mid-2024.

These and other potential implemented actions under project dissemination will be described in the following report of Communication, Dissemination and Training Activities report by March 2025.

5. Conclusion

During the first 15 months of SPINMATE, communication dissemination and training activities have played a pivotal role in sharing knowledge and engaging stakeholders effectively. By employing a collaborative effort from all partners, including regular project updates, workshops and events participation, and organisation of an interactive webinar, the project team has successfully fostered a robust sense of collaboration among stakeholders, including scientists, engineers, industry partners, and parallel projects/clusters. This proactive engagement has not only facilitated the efficient exchange of critical insights and innovative solutions but has also paved the way for seamless knowledge dissemination, resulting in widespread awareness and appreciation of the project's advancements. As a result, the project has not only achieved remarkable progress in solid-state battery technology but has also set a compelling example of how transparent and inclusive communication can drive the success of complex scientific endeavours.

This holistic approach has not only expedited progress in solid-state battery technology but has also enabled stakeholders to leverage the project's findings, ensuring a broader and lasting impact across the industry. The project remarkable steps to the profound impact of effective communication, dissemination, and training in advancing cutting-edge technologies towards the industrialisation of SSBs, while fostering collaborative innovation.